

CHARACTERISTICS OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN PREGNANT WOMEN, WOMEN WHO UNDERWENT COVID-19 OUTSIDE PREGNANCY

Yuldasheva Gulchekhra Rakhimovna

Assistant at the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of the ¹Ferghana Institute
of Public Health, Ferghana

Djabbarova Yulduz Kasimovna

Academician of the Medical and Technical Academy of the Russian Federation, MD,
PhD, DSci (Medicine), obstetrician-gynecologist, Professor, Department of
Pharmacology, Physiology, ²Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute, Tashkent,
Uzbekistan;

Musakhodjaeva Dilorom Abdullaevna

PhD, Doctor of Biological Sciences, Head of the Laboratory Reproductive
Immunology of the ³Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics of the Academy
of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Summary. 118 pregnant women from 12 to 37 weeks of gestation who were admitted to the Fergana Regional Perinatal Center were examined. Pregnancy occurred 2-10 months after the viral infection, as evidenced by IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV-2. The control group consisted of 72 women at the same time frame with a physiological pregnancy. A pathological imbalance in the cytokine status with a predominance of pro-inflammatory cytokines was revealed, which indicates the presence of an inflammatory reaction of a certain activity as a manifestation of the post-Covid syndrome and pathogenetically determines the development of complications of the gestational process.

Key words: pregnant women, cytokines, post-Covid syndrome.

HOMILADORLIKDAN OLDIN COVID-19 NI YUQTIRGAN HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA SITOKIN HOLATINING XUSUSIYATLARI

Yuldasheva Gulchehra Rahimovna

Farg‘ona Xalq salomatligi instituti 1-akusherlik va ginekologiya
kafedrası assistenti

Djabbarova Yulduz Qosimovna

Rossiya Federatsiyasi Tibbiyot-texnika akademiyasi akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari
doktori, akusher-ginekolog, Toshkent pediatriya tibbiyot instituti farmakologiya,
fiziologiya kafedrası professori, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

Musaxodjaeva Dilorom Abdullaevna

biologiya fanlari doktori, O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasi Inson
immunologiyasi va genomikasi instituti immunologiya reproduksiyasi laboratoriyani
mudiri, Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

Annotatsiya: Farg‘ona viloyat perinatal markaziga yotqizilgan 12 dan 37
haftagacha bo‘lgan 118 nafar homilador ayolni tekshirdik, homiladorlik virusli
infeksiyadan 2-10 oy o‘tgach sodir bo‘lganligi SARS-CoV-2 ga IgG antikorlari
mavjudligidan dalolat beradi. Nazorat guruhi fiziologik homiladorlik bilan bir
vaqtning o‘zida 72 ayoldan iborat edi. Yallig‘lanishni keltirib chiqaradigan
sitokinlarning ustunligi bilan sitokin holatida patologik nomutanosiblik aniqlandi, bu
post-Covid sindromining namoyon bo‘lishi sifatida ma‘lum bir faoliyatning
yallig‘lanish reaksiyasi mavjudligini ko‘rsatadi va homiladorlik jarayonining
asoratlari rivojlanishini patogenetik jihatdan aniqlaydi.

Kalit so‘zlar: homilador ayollar, sitokinlar, post-Covid sindromi

**ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ЦИТОКИНОВОГО СТАТУСА У БЕРЕМЕННЫХ,
ЖЕНЩИН, ПЕРЕНЕСШИХ COVID-19 ВНЕ БЕРЕМЕННОСТИ**

Резюме. Обследованы 118 беременных женщин в сроках от 12 до 37 недель
гестации, которые поступили в Ферганский областной перинатальный центр
**Беременность наступила через 2-10 месяцев после перенесенной вирусной
инфекции, о чем свидетельствовали антитела класса IgG к SARS-CoV-2 .**

Контрольную группу составили 72 женщины в тех же сроках с физиологически протекающей беременностью. Выявлен патологический дисбаланс в цитокиновом статусе с превалированием провоспалительных цитокинов, что свидетельствует о наличии воспалительной реакции определенной активности как проявления постковидного синдрома и патогенетически обуславливают развитие осложнений гестационного процесса.

Ключевые слова: беременные, цитокины, постковидный синдром

Relevance. Clinical observations show long-term negative consequences of COVID-19 on various human organs and systems (musculoskeletal system, lungs, myocardium, brain functions, etc.) [3. P.8]. Currently, there is still very little data on the long-term effect of coronavirus infection on the course of pregnancy in women who have had COVID-19 before conception. However, it is known that coronavirus affects the state of the immune system, in particular the level of cytokines [1. P. 1.; 2.P.1] Thus, a number of authors associate deaths in COVID-19 with a sustained increase in the levels of IL-6 and IL-1. The physiological course of pregnancy over time is ensured by a certain balance of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines. Based on the above, we set ourselves **the goal:** to identify the features of the synthesis of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines in the blood serum of pregnant women who underwent COVID-19 in the preconception period. **Material and methods.** 118 pregnant women from 12 to 37 weeks of gestation who were admitted to the Fergana Regional Perinatal Center were examined. Pregnancy occurred 2-10 months after the viral infection, as evidenced by IgG antibodies to SARS-CoV-2. The control group consisted of 72 women at the same time frame with a physiological pregnancy. Immunological studies were carried out by determining the content of cytokines IL-1 β , IL-4, IL-6, IL-8, IFN α and IFN γ in blood serum using the ELISA method (test system of LLC “Vector Best”, Russian Federation). The obtained data were processed by the method of variation statistics with the determination of reliability $p < 0.05$. **Results and discussion.** The results of the studies showed that pregnant women were in the age range of 22 - 40 years, with the bulk of 56,3% being women aged 31 to 40 years. 66.9% women had a mild form of infection, 22.9% -had a

moderate form, and 10.2% - a severe form of infection. The most frequently diagnosed somatic pathologies were iron deficiency anemia – $56.8\pm 4.5\%$ and metabolic syndrome – in $29.7\pm 4.2\%$ of pregnant women. There was a threat of miscarriage in 71%, spontaneous abortion occurred in 33%, premature birth occurred in 11%. Analysis of the results of pro-inflammatory cytokines showed that the level of IL-1 β in pregnant women in the first trimester was significantly higher than control values by 1.3 times ($p<0.05$) and in the third trimester - by 1.2 times ($p<0.05$). The level of IL-6 in all patients exceeded control values throughout pregnancy ($p<0.05$). The level of IL-8 was increased in patients in the first trimester by 1.4 times ($p<0.05$), in the second trimester - by 2.5 times and in the third trimester – by 3.6 times in comparison with similar indicators with physiological ongoing pregnancy ($p<0.05$). It was found that the level of the anti-inflammatory cytokine IL-4 was 1.3 times lower than the control values in the examined patients ($P<0.05$). **Conclusions.** The identified pathological imbalance in the cytokine status with a predominance of pro-inflammatory cytokines indicates the presence of an inflammatory reaction of a certain activity in the body of pregnant women. It should be considered that these manifestations of post-Covid syndrome pathogenetically determine the development of complications of the gestational process. The time has come to recognize the need to develop an immunological approach to the prevention of prematurity and other complications of the perinatal period in women who have had coronavirus infection.

Literature:

1. Calabrese C., Rajendram P, Sacha G. L Calabrese L. Practical aspects of targeting IL-6 in COVID-19 disease//Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine October 2020. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3949/ccjm.87a.ccc018>.
2. McGonagle D, Sharif K, O'Regan A, Bridgewood C. The role of cytokines including interleukin-6 in COVID-19 induced pneumonia and macrophage activation syndrome-like disease. Autoimmun Rev 2020; 19(6):102537. DOI:10.1016/j.autrev.2020.102537.

3. Sinchikhin S.P., Stepanyan L.V., Mamiev O.B. New coronavirus infection and other respiratory viral diseases in pregnant women. Gynecology. 2020. – Т.22. – No. 2. - With. 6–16.[in Rush]. Синчихин С.П, Степанян Л.В., Мамиев О.Б. Новая коронавирусная инфекция //Гинекология. 2020. – Т.22. – №2. - с. 6–16.